

THE ROLE OF LOCALIZATION AND TRANSCREATION IN THE TRANSLATION OF COMMERCIAL ADVERTISEMENTS FROM ENGLISH INTO AZERBAIJANI**Nargiz Novruzlu Ilham,***MA in Translation**Khazar University, Azerbaijan***Supervisor: Orujova Irina***PhD in Comparative Typological Linguistics*

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Abstract

The paper studies the role of localization and transcreation in the translation of commercial advertisements from English into Azerbaijani. The study begins by discussing the language of advertisement and its role in promoting products and services. Cultural, linguistic aspects and possible challenges are examined. Then, the focus shifts to localization and creative translation.

Overall, the paper analyses main challenges, key principles, and benefits of using both localization and transcreation through a qualitative analysis of original advertisement samples.

Keywords: advertisement, translation, localization, transcreation**Introduction**

The translation of commercial advertisements plays an important role in reaching diverse audiences in different countries. As global brands continue to expand increasingly, the need for accurate and culturally relevant advertisement translation becomes vital. The translation of commercial advertisements goes beyond literal translation and requires the comprehensive understanding of both the source and target cultures. So, during the translation process, translators may face some linguistic and cultural challenges. In this case, one of the main strategies used to overcome such difficulties are localization and transcreation. Localization mainly deals with the technical aspects of translation, such as colours, visuals, units of measurement, pricing, cultural references, date and time formats. However, transcreation employs the rearrangement of advertising texts especially when advertising messages are accompanied by visuals.

The language of advertisement

Advertisement is the promotion of a product, service, event, or idea to draw attention and influence the target audience. It aims to constantly motivate individuals to purchase and utilize the advertised product, while persuading them that it surpasses the competing brands they currently employ. [4] Advertisement language is an important communication tool. Here, the message is one sided, from producer to consumers. [1] The language of advertisement is designed to be catchy, memorable, and concise with its primary goal being to leave lasting message. One of the main characteristics of advertisements is the use of neologisms, new invented words, rhetorical devices such as metaphors, puns, repetitions, personifications etc. Sometimes advertisements may be accompanied by music and visuals.

The language of Azerbaijani advertisements is also clear and concise. For example: "Hər damlasında həyat var" (the slogan of Sirab), "Sənə yaxın gələcək" (the slogan of Azercell). The elements of Azerbaijani culture, such as traditional music, images and references to traditions and customs are the main features of

our advertisements. Figurative language is also used in the original Azerbaijani advertisements.

As there are a lot of global brands that promote their products in Azerbaijan, the translation process is inevitable. Sometimes, this process can be challenging as there are different cultural and linguistic nuances between English and Azerbaijani. It may become more challenging when an advertising text is accompanied by a visual. In such situations, translators use different techniques or strategies to overcome the challenges. The most common ones are localization and transcreation.

Localization

The main purpose of international brands is to appeal to more people all over the world. The essence of global advertising is to convey the same message to people in different cultures and have the same impact on them. It can be done through a translation process. One of the well-known strategies that translators use in translation of commercial advertisements is localization.

Translators especially use this strategy, when there are a lot of cultural nuances between the source and target text. The word "localization" is derived from the English word "local". Localization goes beyond translation and focuses on translating cultural references as well as adapting images to a target market. During this process, exact equivalents are added to the words that are being translated and their meanings are preserved. So, it doesn't only cover the translation of texts, but also product features, images, symbols, colours, cultural references, date and time formats, pricing, units of measurement, legal and regulatory compliance, branding and messaging, marketing content, promotion channels etc.

During localization process, a translator should ensure that the product will be experienced in the same way by the target audience. In other words, it should be rearranged to make target audiences feel as if the content is specially created for them. So, a translator should have a comprehensive knowledge about both languages and cultures. There are some factors that should be

taken into consideration, during localization process. Here, technical processes are very important. One of them involves considering colours and visuals during translation.

Colours play an important role in advertisements because they have a physiological effect on people. They are non-verbal foregrounded features of an advertisement. The main point is that colours also differ from culture to culture. The colour which has a positive meaning in one culture, can have a negative meaning in another. For example, "white" symbolizes "purity", "innocence" in most cultures including English and Azerbaijani, but it represents sadness in Japan. In the same way, "black" represents "sadness" in most cultures, but it may not be the same in the others. These nuances should be considered by advertisers, as well as translators.

Visual is also an important part of advertisements. They make an advertisement more interesting, catchy, and memorable. Translation of advertising text which consists of a visual can sometimes be very challenging. One of the reasons is that as colours, they may also consist of symbols which have different meanings in various cultures. Then, the visual which is appropriate for one culture, may be inappropriate for another. In this time, the visuals should be adapted to the target culture.

Another factor is localizing the design and layout of the translated text to the local language. For example, language orientation is left to right in Azerbaijani, but it is right to left in Arabic. So, it is also one of the aspects that should be adapted considering the target language.

Moreover, making changes in currency, measurement units, date and time formats requires localization. For example, it is written as month/day/year in US English, but in British English and Azerbaijani the date format follows the day/month/year order. Then, currency unit is the pound sterling in England, dollar in the USA, and manat in Azerbaijan. Additionally, imperial measurement is feet in America, but meter in Azerbaijan.

During localizing, a translator should know the essence of the advertising text. Because sometimes a word may have more than one meaning. As the purpose of advertising text is being memorable, a lot of wordplays, tropes, rhetorical devices are used to attract the attention of consumers. English is very flexible language, so it is easy to construct different grammatical sentence structures. But, in these situations, translators often face challenges. This time, the context should be examined, and appropriate strategy should be carefully selected.

Localizing is not a simple process. Global markets thoroughly explore the target culture before localizing their brand. As it is mentioned, it does not only involve the translation process, also the whole cultural nuances in advertisements, such as localizing images, videos, music, websites, even menus of the restaurants. For example, in some countries where local drinks are preferred, global brands such as McDonald's offer local drink alternatives such as tea in Azerbaijan. Global brands also use beliefs, family concepts, holidays in their advertisements. Including England, while living

alone is very usual in some countries, living with families is common in others. By using this, advertisers also include such factors to advertisements. For example, on Nowruz holiday, Coca-Cola promotes its drinks in Azerbaijan by using our traditional holiday and family concept. The brand also shows our customs, traditions and uses our national music in its advertising video.

One of the best examples of localization is Coca-Cola's "Share a Coke" campaign. The brand conducted research and identified the most common names in each country and labelled bottles with the names. For example, in England the labels were as "Sonia" or "Marcus". In Azerbaijan, they were as "Anar" or "Ülkər". Also, the countries in which it was impolite to refer someone with their first names such as China, the bottles were designed as "friend", "family", or "classmate".

Transcreation

The word "transcreation" is derived from the words "translation" and "creation". As its name implies, transcreation means creative translation. It is the combination of translation, creation, and copywriting. Transcreation is commonly used in advertising translation in which cultural nuances are very essential. According to Pedersen transcreation is transferring brands and messages from one culture to another. [3]

During a direct translation, advertising texts and especially slogans may lose their meaning as they may contain puns, metaphors, alliterations etc. These writings cannot be translated literally into other languages. It involves cultural and linguistic touches while remaining faithful to the essence of the original text. In this process, as it is not translated word-for-word, the text can be recreated again and bear little resemblance to the original language. Here, the differences between the target and source language play an important role. Eugene Nida and Charles Taber also perceive linguistic and cultural differences as a problem and approach the translation of culture by underlining the fact that the elements to be transferred must adapt to the realities of the target culture recipient. [2]

Most times, transcreation can be very challenging because a translator should have very good translating as well as writing skills. The transcreation experts are also writers. They feel free to make some changes in the text such as adding new words and phrases, rearranging figures of speech and revising sentence structures, and even removing some words. If it is appropriate, subheadings, footnotes, and brief summaries can also be added.

Sometimes, there are idioms in the slogans of advertisements. As it is known, idioms are specific to one culture and carry a figurative meaning so it cannot be translated literally. In this case, the idiom will lose its meaning. Generally, when global markets face such challenges, they choose to transcreate their slogan for each individual market. But it does not only end up with idioms.

The advertisement also may consist of a jingle. Jingle is a short catchy and memorable tune or song used for advertising purposes. Some jingles have lyrics which are simple and repetitive. When the products are promoted in different countries, there is a need for the translation of jingles. It is very challenging to translate

rhyiming couples because the rhyiming scheme should be maintained. It can be done with transcreation process.

The advertisement of "Haribo" can be a good sample for transcreation. Haribo is a well-known confectionary brand. It is almost promoted all over the world and known to everybody. Transcreation is used in the translation of its slogan and jingle: "Kids and Grownups love it so, the happy world of Haribo" (the slogan of Haribo). If it is translated word-for-word in Azerbaijani it will be "Uşaqlar və böyükklər bunu çox sevirlər, Haribonun xoşbəxt dünyası. The sentence will be incomplete and will not convey any meaning. If we try to correct it and translate as "Haribonun xoşbəxt (və ya sevgidolu) dünyasını uşaqlar və böyükklər çox sevirlər". It will be grammatically correct but quite problematic in terms of meaning and harmony. The real translation of this slogan in Azerbaijani is: "Uşaq ya da böyük ol, Hariboyla xoşbəxt ol". Here, the text rearranged again. There is also a grammatical shift. The source text is declarative but the target text is imperative sentence. It becomes different but it is correct in terms of grammar, meaning and harmony. As well as the rhyiming scheme is preserved, and it also sounds like a music.

Then, one of the famous slogans is McDonald's "I'm lovin' it" (the slogan of McDonald's). Although the slogan is short, it is challenging to translate to different languages. It is a short form of: "I am loving it". Grammatically, the stative verb "love" is not used in the present continuous tense. However, in this slogan, it is employed in the present continuous tense. It makes it more catchy, memorable, and unique. In some languages there is not present continuous tense form including Azerbaijani. So, during the translation process, there is a shift in grammatical structure. It is translated into Azerbaijani as "Bax, budur sevdiiyim". The slogan is reshaped and the intended meaning is preserved.

Another example of transcreation is used in the advertising text of "Magnum". It is a famous brand of an ice-cream. The brand uses attention-grabbing sentences, phrases and visuals in its advertisements. Generally, the visuals and advertising texts are connected to each other. So, it may create a challenge during translation process. For example, in one of the visuals of Magnum, a half of a beast (tiger, lion) and a half of person (woman or man) is shown and it is accompanied by the sentence "Release the Beast" (Magnum). It is translated into Azerbaijani as "İçindəki səni sərbəst burax". Both the source and target text are imperative sentences. Here, literal translation is not used during translation. Because with literal translation, the target audience will not be able to understand the intended meaning of this sentence. The translator adds new words into the target text and omitted the word "beast". So, transcreation is used as the text is rearranged. The word

"beast" is not translated because it has a negative meaning in the target language. However, it is used metaphorically in the source text to denote a positive meaning.

To my mind, the translation is successful although the target text itself cannot reflect the image. As it is known, the main goal of advertisement translation is to deliver the intended meaning of the text. In this translation, the intended meaning is maintained and delivered effectively to the target audience.

As shown above, this sample involves both linguistic and cultural challenges. To translate this advertising text effectively, the translator should know deeply both cultures and languages. Then, he/she should pay attention to the context and think about to connect the text and visual.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the use of localization and transcreation in the translation of commercial advertisements from English into Azerbaijani is essential for effective translation. By using localization, translators mainly deal with the technical aspects of translation such as visuals, colours, units of measurement, currency, date, and time formats. To reach more audiences and attract attention, brands also use localization in their visuals, websites, music even menus of restaurants. However, transcreation is a creative translation which is used in rearranging advertising texts. It goes beyond translation and helps to create a text while preserving its intended meaning. Transcreation is very beneficial especially in translation of advertising texts which consist of rhetorical devices and are accompanied by visuals and music. Both localization and transcreation are very effective in translating advertising texts especially if they involve a lot of cultural nuances.

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